

Supplemental Table S1. Effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 1.5 L of either AF, TMR, or E* on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current period** -1 and 0

Variable	ANOVA (Type III SS)								
	Treatment			Current relative to MPP			Interaction		
	DF***	chisq	p-value	DF***	chisq	p-value	DF***	chisq	p-value
RIC registered visits	2	7.02	0.03	1	13.75	<0.01	2	8.93	0.01
Confident visits	2	7.03	0.03	1	9.67	<0.01	2	5.58	0.06
Unsuccessful attempts	2	0.49	0.78	1	0.48	0.49	2	9.26	<0.01

*AF: 200 g or 1.5 L of alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), TMR: 1.5 L of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=8), and E: an empty bin (n=4)

**Periods were 48-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.

***Numerator DF obtained from the ANOVA type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>)

Supplemental Table S2. Back-transformed means and SE for models analyzing the effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 1.5 L of either AF, TMR, or E* on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current periods** -1 and 0

Variable	Treatment											
	AF				TMR				E			
	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit
RIC registered visits	5.13	1.06	3.36	7.84	5.64	0.87	4.11	7.74	2.95	0.76	1.74	5.01
Confident visits	4.46	0.98	2.84	6.99	5.21	0.85	3.73	7.28	2.26	0.65	1.25	4.08
Unsuccessful attempts	2.64	1.47	0.84	8.33	1.63	0.8	0.59	4.49	0.61	0.5	0.11	3.33

*AF: 200 g or 1.5 L of alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), TMR: 1.5 L of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=8), and E: an empty bin (n=4)

**Periods were 48-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.

Supplemental Table S3. Effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 1.5 L of either AF or TMR* on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current periods** -4 and 0

Variable	ANOVA (Type III SS)								
	Treatment			Current relative to MPP			Interaction		
	DF***	chisq	p-value	DF***	chisq	p-value	DF***	chisq	p-value
RIC registered visits	1	0.27	0.60	1	15.36	<0.01	1	8.39	<0.01
Confident visits	1	0.32	0.57	1	15.01	<0.01	1	7.31	<0.01
Unsuccessful attempts	1	0.00	0.96	1	0.31	0.58	1	5.16	0.02
% Intake	1	4.63	0.03	1	2.56	0.11	1	2.00	0.16

*AF: 200 g or 1.5 L of alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), TMR: 1.5 L of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=8)

**Periods were 48-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.

***Numerator DF obtained from the ANOVA type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>)

Supplemental Table S4. Back-transformed means and SE for models analyzing the effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 1.5 L of either AF or TMR on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current periods** -4 to 0

Variable	Treatment							
	AF				TMR			
	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit
RIC registered visits	8.47	0.96	6.75	10.64	5.95	0.57	4.90	7.22
Confident visits	7.33	1.07	5.47	9.83	5.30	0.64	4.15	6.76
Unsuccessful attempt	2.58	0.97	1.21	5.50	1.39	0.45	0.73	2.66
% Intake	73.00	5.34	61.40	82.10	64.10	4.30	55.30	72.00

*AF: 200 g or 1.5 L of alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), TMR: 1.5 L of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=8)

**Periods were 48-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.